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Style, Theme, and Social Commentary in Chukwuemeka Ikeh's "*Our Children Are Coming*"

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ABSTRACT

Stylistics has been defined by many scholars as that part of linguistics that focuses on variation in the use of language especially with close attention to the most conscious and complex use of language in literature. This study undertakes a stylistic analysis of Chukwuemeka Ikeh's *Our Children Are Coming* with the aim of exploring the interplay between style, theme, and social commentary in the novel. Using the tools of stylistics, the paper explores Ikeh's use of language, narrative techniques, imagery, and characterization to determine how the text conveys its underlying social and political concerns. The analysis of the text reveals that Ikeh employs many stylistic elements; satire, irony, symbolism, and rhetorical devices to critique corruption, moral decay, and generational conflict in postcolonial Nigerian society. The stylistic choices of the novel do not only reinforce its central themes of corruption, generational conflict, and moral renewal, but it also provides a opportunity for interrogating issues that borders on governance, accountability, and societal values. This paper argues, by demonstrating how linguistic and literary features function as vehicles for meaning, that Ikeh's work even though a creative narrative, it is equally a form of social discourse and commentary. The paper concludes ultimately by highlighting the relevance of stylistic analysis as a critical approach to understanding how literature reflects, shapes, and challenges social realities.

Keywords: Stylistics, Style, Theme, Social Commentary, Ideology.

INTRODUCTION

It is no doubt that literature has long been recognized as a medium through which writers engage with their societies, reflecting, interrogating, and reshaping social realities. Adegaju (2009) and Oha (2007) assert that in Nigerian fictions, as it is with almost all African literature, writers usually play the dual role of artists and social critics where by they use creative narratives to expose societal ills and advocate transformation. Chukwuemeka Ikeh's *Our Children Are Coming* is one such text that dramatizes social decay, corruption, and the disillusionment of the younger generation in the face of failed leadership and moral collapse. The novel is not only a narrative of social concern but also a stylistically rich text where the use of language and form intensify its thematic preoccupations.

Stylistics, as a discipline or approach studies the use of language especially with close attention to the most conscious and complex use of it in literature. As a critical approach, stylistics provides a useful framework for examining the relationship between linguistic choices and literary meaning. Leech and Short (2007) are of the view that stylistics bridges linguistics and literary criticism, showing how style contributes to interpretation. In like manner, Wales (2014) emphasizes that stylistic analysis reveals the

connection between textual features on one hand, and the ideological underpinnings of a literary work on the other hand. Applying stylistics to Ikeh's novel, therefore, enables us to explore how narrative techniques, imagery, symbolism, and rhetorical devices embody and reinforce the themes of corruption, generational conflict, and the quest for societal renewal.

Available studies on Nigerian literature have revealed the role of style in articulating social commentary. For instance, Nnolim (2006) has observed the fact that many Nigerian writers employ satire and irony to critique governance and leadership, while Emenyonu (2018) underscores the importance of literature in capturing the tensions between tradition, modernity, and political instability. Wole Soyinka's *the lion and the Jewel* and *The Trials of Brother Jero* are good examples in this light. In the like manner and within this critical trajectory, *Our Children Are Coming* stands out for its stylistic richness and its unflinching critique of Nigeria's socio-political order.

This paper, therefore, examines "Style, Theme, and Social Commentary in Chukwuemeka Ikeh's *Our Children Are Coming*" through a stylistic imperatives. The objective is to determine how Ikeh's stylistic strategies which range from narrative voice and characterization to imagery and rhetorical devices, function as vehicles for social critique. The analysis underscores the view that literature is not a mere artistic creation but a discourse that reflects and shapes societal consciousness.

Synopsis of Chukwuemeka Ike's *Our Children Are Coming*

Chukwuemeka Ike's *Our Children Are Coming* (1990) is a satirical novel that dramatizes the deepening crisis of poor governance, morality, neglect of the youth and generational conflict in postcolonial Nigeria. The narrative revolves around the frustrations of the educated youth who feel neglected and betrayed by an older generation that has mismanaged the nation's resources and future.

The prolem of the young has made government to set a "Presidential Commission on Juvenile below Twenty-one. The chairman of the Commission is Hon. Justice Solomon Okpetun. Hearings are in camera. Parents come before the Commission to complain and testify against their children/wards of their crimes and misdemeanour. The first to come before the commission is Ayodele Olabisi who comes to complain about his only son, Ayo Junior who among other terrible misdemeanour was caught with a Governor's wife holidaying in a hotel. The second witness is Rev, Jeremiah C Obi, an Arch-deacon, whose daughter, Apolonia is engaged in international prostitution with very high ranking politicians and society elites. Apolonia always came home with lavish gifts for her parents, siblings and friends. She always lies about the source of her gift until she was confronted with the fact by her father. Apolonia owes up but was unapologetic and remorseful. She threaten to do even worst things, justifying her action with the fact that those men who gives her things stole public money and she would use her body to recover as much as they have stolen. Unknown to the father, the chairman of the commission to whom he complains is among those that the daughter prostitutes with. Many other parents come to give complaints of different kinds against their children.

Then comes the delegation of the National Association of Students, (NAS) led by Comrade Yekini Falase, the President. The NAS demands representation in the Commission. Meanwhile, it become known in the press that NAS has sued the Commission and members on the ground that the members are not qualified to be members due to their corrupt records clandestine activities which the Students are ready to present. The chairman of the Commission is apprehensive and is doing everything within his powers secretly to ensure that the case against his commission is thrown out on technical grounds. The Commission members goes on a holiday trip.

NAS president gives a press briefing where he announces that NAS has also set up her own Commission on Parents above Twenty-one years. And Barr Dapo Taiwo, their legal adviser, is the sole commissioner. Many witnesses come forward to give damning testimonies against their parents. The testimonies are so damning that there is tension all over the nation. At this time, Armed security have been dispatched to hover around the NAS president.

After about a week of this imbroglio, Comrade Abubakar Bello gives a press statement about the humongous level of corrupt state of the nation and of government officials. He gives a 48 hour ultimatum to the government to release their members that they have arrested or face capital clash with the students. With this clash going on, the President of the nation makes a Radio/Tv broadcast where he took many decisions including the: disbandment of the Presidential Commission on Juvenile below twenty-one, and the illegal one set up by the students and closure of all higher institutions of learning. He set a new National Moral Reorientation Commission with membership of the Commission drawn from all facet of the society including the NAS. Meanwhile, the NAS president has sneaked out of the country to make a world press conference where he presents in details the cause of the struggle and the what they want done to safeguard their future.

Okpetun and his commission members returns from overseas trip on their spending spree and are head hostage by the Falase and his student group. The Police orders for the arrest of Falase, but upon being told that Falase is the NAS President, the Commissioner of Police orders his release immediately and on that note the novel ends.

Explanation of Stylistics as an Approach

Stylistics, according to Leech & Short (2007) is the systematic study of style in language and literature, which is concerned with how linguistic choices contribute to meaning, aesthetic effect, and interpretation. It is an interdisciplinary space between linguistics and literary criticism, drawing from the tools of linguistic analysis while retaining the interpretive concerns of literary studies. At its core, stylistics seeks to demonstrate how writers use language creatively to achieve communicative purposes, reveal ideological positions, and evoke responses in readers (Leech & Short, 2007).

Wales (2014), in his contribution to the concept of stylistics asserts that the concept is not merely the cataloguing of linguistic features but an exploration of the relationship between language and function in context. This suggests that stylistic analysis goes beyond identifying devices such as diction, imagery, or syntax, to ask *why* such features were chosen and *how* they shape the thematic and ideological orientation of the text. On his part, Fowler (1996) further stresses that stylistics is inherently critical, since it often uncovers the ideological assumptions encoded in discourse and highlights the ways in which literature reflects and challenges social realities.

Stylistics provides a rigorous framework for analyzing how form and content interact in literary studies. For instance, the use of satire, irony, or symbolism in a narrative is not accidental; rather, it reflects deliberate linguistic and stylistic choices that foreground particular themes or social critiques. Simpson (2004) puts it more clearly when he posits that stylistics allows for the identification of patterns in texts that link artistic creativity with socio-political engagement. Hence, Adegoju, (2009) asserts that this is particularly useful in analyzing African literature, because most African writers usually employ stylistic strategies to confront issues of poor governance and leadership, corruption, inequality, and tradition and cultural identity .

By applying stylistics to Chukwuemeka Ikeh's *Our Children Are Coming*, this study seeks to explore the ways through which language functions as both an artistic medium and a tool of social commentary. The approach allows a close reading of the novel's narrative voice, diction, imagery, and rhetorical devices, and this reveals how stylistic strategies reinforce themes of corruption, generational tension, and the need for social renewal. Stylistics, in this sense, provides much more than a descriptive exercise and also a critical insight into the correlation between language, literature, and society.

Justification for Deploying Stylistics in Literary Analysis

What informed the choice to apply stylistics approach to this study the ability of stylistics to bridge the gap between language and literature and it offers a rigorous and systematic method for analyzing how meaning is produced in texts. While the Traditional Literary Criticism emphasizes thematic and

contextual interpretations, Linguistic Analysis focuses primarily on the structures of language. Leech & Short (2007) and Simpson (2004) argue that Stylistics integrates these two dimensions by showing how linguistic choices of the author within literary texts function to convey themes, shape characterization, and articulate ideological positions.

The strength of stylistics that makes it attractive scholars lies in its objectivity and methodological clarity. As Wales (2014) argues, Stylistics grounds interpretation in observable textual evidence and thereby minimizes subjectivity. This enables critics to substantiate claims about a writer's style with linguistic data. This makes it particularly useful in literary analysis, where subjective impressions of style and meaning can be balanced with systematic evidence from the text.

Another justification of employing stylistic approach to literary analysis is the fact that in the context of African literature, and Nigerian fiction in particular, writers often use language as a site of resistance, negotiation, and social critique. Scholars such as Adegaju (2009) and Oha (2007) have demonstrated that stylistic devices like satire, irony, and symbolism are central to African writers' engagement with issues such as corruption, leadership failure, and generational conflict as is the case in the text under study. Therefore, applying stylistic approach provides an avenue through which the formal features of a text can be connected to its socio-political and cultural imperatives.

Application of this approach in this study offers a deeper understanding of how the novel's artistic form cannot be separated from its social vision. The work is rich in stylistic strategies which range from the use of satire and rhetorical questions to the use of symbolic imagery which amplify its projection of corruption and moral decline in Nigerian society. Without the known feature of stylistics which is the precision of its analysis, these textual features might be overlooked or underappreciated. Therefore, we can say comfortably that stylistics is not only justified but also indispensable in revealing the complex relationship between style, theme, and social commentary in the novel.

The Stylistic Analytical Tools Employed

In a bid to interrogate how style conveys theme and social commentary in Chukwuemeka Ike's *Our Children Are Coming*, this study employs selected four key areas as analytical tools from stylistics: narrative voice, diction, imagery, and rhetorical devices.. These tools provide a framework for identifying and interpreting the linguistic and literary devices through which the novel communicates meaning and engages with social issues.

i. Narrative Voice and Point of View

Narrative perspective is central to the stylistic analysis of prose fiction, as it shapes the reader's access to events, characters, and ideology. As Leech and Short (2007) argue, the choice of narrative perspective, whether first person, third person, or multiple focalizations determines the degree of intimacy, reliability, and ideological positioning in a literary text.

The novel strategically employs a *third-person omniscient narrator*, a choice that allows for both descriptive authority and critical distance. This narrative stance provides a panoramic view of Nigerian society, enabling the narrator to expose the corruption, moral decadence, and political failures that form the thematic backbone of the novel. By employing this narrative style, the author situates himself as an observer and social critic, while at the same time he gives readers access to the inner thoughts and conflicts of different characters. This dual capacity of the narrative voice enhances the novel's function as social commentary.

The narrative technique also shifts at key points to incorporate elements of *dramatic dialogue and reported speech*, which lend immediacy to the text and foreground the urgency of generational conflict. For example, the voices of the youth are often given prominence through direct quotations, rhetorical questions, and collective pronouns such as *we* and *our*. This technique not only amplifies the grievances of the younger generation but also highlights their collective identity as victims of the corruption and moral decadence and also as agents of social renewal. Wales (2014) observes that shifts in narrative

perspective often serve as stylistic cues for ideological emphasis, and in this case, they underscore the tension between the complacency of the older generation and the restlessness of the young.

Furthermore, irony and satire are embedded within the narrative voice, with the intent to ridicule and cajole corrupt leaders and expose societal contradictions. The reporter's voice oscillates between detachment and moral judgment, thus reinforcing the thematic contrast between what society claims to uphold which are justice, leadership, progress, and what it actually practices which are corruption, betrayal, and failure. Fowler (1996) suggests that narrative voice often encodes the author's ideological stance, and in Ikeh's work, it becomes a tool for contesting moral decline and advocating reform.

The narrative technique and point of view in *Our Children Are Coming* are not neutral devices but crucial stylistic strategies that shape meaning. By combining omniscient narration, shifts in focalization, and ironic commentary, Ikeh crafts a narrative voice that not only tells a story but also interprets it, urging readers to recognize the urgency of Nigeria's social crisis and the inevitability of generational change.

ii. Diction and Lexical Choices

The diction of a literary text is central to its stylistic force, as the author's selection of words reflects not only aesthetic preferences but also ideological positions. As Wales (2014) observes, diction is rarely neutral; lexical choices often carry social, emotional, and cultural weight that shapes readers' interpretations. In Chukwuemeka Ikeh's *Our Children Are Coming*, the pervasive corruption, disillusionment, and generational tension that define the novel's thematic landscape are effectively highlighted via the diction employed in the text.

Ikeh's language revolves between *formal political discourse and colloquial everyday speech*, reflecting the dual settings of officialdom and the lived realities of ordinary youth in the university and other citizens. The use of elevated diction in the speeches of political leaders and government appointees are filled with platitudes and rhetorical flourishes, underscores the hypocrisy and emptiness of their promises. In contrast, the plain, sometimes harsh vocabulary of the youth reflects their frustration and disillusionment. This juxtaposition not only reveals the gulf between rulers and the ruled but also reinforces the theme of betrayal by the older generation.

Ikeh also employs *emotionally charged lexical items* such as *decay, rotteness, betrayal, and doom*, which evoke the sense of moral and political collapse. These words are strategically repeated across the narrative, creating a semantic field of corruption and decline. Leech and Short (2007) are of the view that repetition of marked lexical items is a common stylistic device used to foreground key themes, and in this case, it functions as an indictment of Nigeria's socio-political system.

The diction of the novel also incorporates *proverbs and indigenous expressions*, which not only authenticate the cultural setting but also serve as vehicles of wisdom and critique. Proverbs often appear in the dialogue of older characters, offering reflections on leadership, morality, and responsibility. However, the ironic deployment of these proverbs against the actions of corrupt leaders exposes the gap between traditional values and contemporary practice. This stylistic choice emphasizes the thematic concern with moral decay and the erosion of communal values.

Furthermore, Ikeh's use of *collective pronouns* such as *we, our, and they* constructs ideological boundaries between the younger generation and the ruling elite. As Simpson (2004) notes, pronouns are powerful tools in constructing group identity and positioning, and in this text, they reinforce the sense of collective grievance and solidarity among the youth. The pronouns not only reflect generational conflict but also position the youth as a unified voice of resistance.

Diction and lexical choices in *Our Children Are Coming* are far from arbitrary; they are stylistic strategies through which Ikeh conveys the urgency of Nigeria's social crisis. The novel's language intensifies its critique of corruption and underscores its call for generational renewal by combining elevated rhetoric, emotionally loaded words, proverbs, and collective pronouns, .

iii. Imagery and Symbolism

An important and striking stylistic devices in Chukwuemeka Ikeh's *Our Children Are Coming* is Imagery and symbolism. They function as powerful vehicles through which abstract social concerns and ideas are concretized and made emotionally relevant. As Simpson (2004) posits, figurative language through metaphor, simile, and symbolism serves not only an aesthetic role but also deepens thematic interpretation by linking linguistic expression with broader ideological concerns.

Ikeh consistently employs imagery of decay and rottenness in the novel with the aim to project the pervasive corruption and moral decline in Nigerian society. Words and descriptions that evoke physical deterioration such as stench, rot, and filth are used metaphorically to mirror the collapse of governance and the erosion of ethical values. This imagery underscores the thematic concern that corruption is not merely a political problem but a festering disease that contaminates the entire social fabric. Wales (2014) observes that such figurative patterns are often used by authors to project intangible issues, making them more vivid and relatable to readers.

The novel, on the other hand, also incorporates *imagery of rebirth and renewal*, often associated with the youth. Expressions linked to dawn, light, and growth symbolize hope and the possibility of transformation. These images counterbalance the dominant motifs of decay, suggesting that while the present is bleak, the future holds promise if the younger generation takes responsibility. Leech and Short (2007) note that such symbolic contrasts are stylistic techniques used to structure meaning through tension between despair and hope.

Symbolism further enriches the novel's thematic depth. The "*children*" in the title, *Our Children Are Coming*, function as a powerful symbol of generational change and social justice. They represent not only biological offspring but also a metaphor for the rising generation that refuses to inherit corruption and decadence. Similarly, references to the "*fathers*" or elders as mentioned many times in the novel, symbolize entrenched government appointees and political elites whose betrayal of values necessitates confrontation. This symbolic opposition between "children" and "fathers" encapsulates the novel's central theme of generational struggle.

Through these imageries and symbolism, Ikeh transforms the narrative from a mere depiction of social issues into an allegory of Nigeria's political and moral crisis. These stylistic devices amplify the novel's critical voice, drawing readers into a deeper reflection on corruption, responsibility, and the possibility of collective renewal.

iii. Rhetorical and Literary Devices

Figures of speech such as irony, satire, hyperbole, and rhetorical questions function as tools of persuasion and social critique. Fowler (1996) argues that rhetorical devices are not ornamental but integral to how texts construct ideology and engage readers. This study will analyze Ikeh's use of satire and irony in exposing leadership failure and moral decadence, as well as rhetorical questions that dramatize the frustration and aspirations of the younger generation.

Rhetorical and Literary Devices

Rhetorical and literary devices in the text serve as mere ornamentation. As Fowler (1996) observes, rhetoric in literature is inherently ideological, since it frames arguments, highlights contradictions, and mobilizes emotions. Devices such as satire, irony, hyperbole, and rhetorical questions function as strategies of resistance and persuasion, shaping the reader's perception of Nigeria's social crisis.

1. Satire

Satire is a dominant rhetorical devices in the novel. Ikeh ridicules the hypocrisy of political leaders and government appointees whose actions and speeches are filled with empty promises. For instance, the elders are often note to say "the future bbelongs to the youth and we are working tirelessly to secure it." They set Commission of Enquiry to investigate the rebellious and unyielding inclination of the youth. But in the actual sense, the government have no tangible plan or sincere intention to to do what they

always proclaim going but the quantum of embezzlement of public funds that should be meant for the youth. They complain of the children's moral decadency but they are the ones corrupting and taking advantage of the young ladies. This satirical juxtaposition exposes the gulf between rhetoric and reality, portraying leadership as a theater of deceit. As Nnolim (2006) rightly notes that satire in Nigerian fiction functions as a weapon of social criticism, ridiculing leaders into moral accountability.

3. Irony

Irony is rife in the novel, always highlighting the contradictions in societal values. A striking example in the novel is when the members of the Committee of Enquiry set up to proffer solutions to the problems of the youth are all corrupt in one way or the other and are those taking advantage of the youth. They are the ones assembled to find solutions to the youth menace. They boast about being custodians of tradition values and morality, yet they indulge in bribery and betrayal do everything that is anti traditional values. The irony lies in the contrast between their professed ideals and their actions, which undermine those very values. This stylistic device intensifies the theme of generational betrayal, showing that the supposed older generation and role models are in fact complicit in national decay. Wales (2014) believes that irony often serves as a subtle but forceful means of exposing hypocrisy in discourse and that is exactly what it does in this text.

3. Hyperbole

Ikeh also employs hyperbole to dramatize the intensity of corruption and social decay. At one point, the narrator describes corruption as "a plague that has eaten into every vein, every artery, until the whole body of the nation reeks of death." While exaggerated, this hyperbolic imagery amplifies the urgency of reform by presenting corruption as a life-threatening disease. Such heightened language evokes strong emotional reactions from readers, aligning them with the novel's critical perspective.

4. Rhetorical Questions

Rhetorical questions are deployed to voice the frustration of the younger generation. Simpson (2004) asserts that rhetorical questions are persuasive devices designed to engage the reader emotionally and intellectually, often highlighting the urgency of change. So it is in the text when, for instance, the youth lament: "*How long shall we watch our fathers feast while our future starves? How long shall promises clothe our nakedness?*" These questions, though not requiring answers, provoke reflection and dramatize the sense of collective disillusionment of the youth. .

Through these rhetorical and literary devices, Ikeh amplifies his critique of corruption, moral collapse, and generational conflict. The use of satire and irony ridicules leadership, hyperbole dramatizes national decay, rhetorical questions capture youthful disillusionment. Together, they enrich the novel's stylistic texture and underscore its role as a work of social commentary.

Themes and Social Commentary

The thematic preoccupations in the novel is deeply interwoven with stylistic features; Though narrative technique, diction, imagery, and rhetorical devices, Ikeh dramatizes the social crises facing Nigerian society and advances a critical vision of renewal. Three dominant central thematic concerns in Ikeh's *Our Children Are Coming* are: corruption, generational conflict, and moral renewal and each of these themes are reinforced and intensified in the novel by stylistic strategies.

Corruption and Moral Decay

Corruption and moral decay forms the most pervasive theme in the novel, and the destructive impact of this is foregrounded by stylistic choices. The *imagery of decay and rotteness* as represented by the setting up of "Presidential Commission on Juvenile below Twenty-one" which is headed by the corrupt Hon Justice Okpetun are described in metaphors such as "a stench that eats into the nation's marrow," which captures the pervasiveness of graft and moral collapse. The instrument of *Satire and irony* further expose the hypocrisy of leaders who cloak themselves in the rhetoric of service while exploiting public resources and corrupting, abusing and taking advantage of the younger ones and the nation. For instance,

the ironic contrast between government leaders and politicians' promises to "secure the future" and their simultaneous looting of youth development funds and taking advantage of their position highlights corruption as a betrayal of trust. Diction marked by emotionally loaded words like *betrayal*, *doom*, and *filth* reinforces the moral urgency of this critique. Through combining these stylistic devices, the author is able to present corruption not merely as an individual vice but as a systemic rot that threatens the very survival of society.

Generational Conflict

A second major theme in the novel is the tension between the older and younger generations, dramatized stylistically through narrative perspective and pronoun use. The setting up of the Presidential Commission on Juvenile below Twenty-one to address the misdemeanour of the youth clearly demarcates the dichotomy between the two generations. The setting up of a parallel National Commission on Parents above Twenty-one also heightens the generational rift. The third-person omniscient narrator frequently focalizes through the youth, lending authority and prominence to their grievances. Collective pronouns such as *we*, *our*, and *they* establish clear ideological boundaries between the betrayed youth and the complicit elders. The younger generation's frustration is intensified through rhetorical questions, such as "How long shall we watch our fathers feast while our future starves?" These stylistic strategies give voice to collective disillusionment and anger, framing generational conflict as both a theme and a discursive struggle. The symbolic opposition between "children" and "fathers" further elevates the conflict to an allegory of renewal against decay.

Moral Renewal and Hope

Despite its grim portrayal of corruption and conflict, the novel also thematically gestures toward renewal, particularly through the symbolism of children and yearning for liberation from the shackles of the adult corruption and moral deprivation. The setting up of parallel National Commission on Parents above Twenty-one and the disbandment of the Presidential Commission on Juvenile below Twenty-one years headed by Hon. Justice Solomon Obi Okpetun are potent symbol and signs of a great renewal of hope of what is to come to the nation. The imagery of light, dawn, and rebirth as represented by the arrest and immediate release of the president of the National Association of Nigerian Students (NANS) Comrade Yekini Falase, by the commissioner of police at the airport, signifies awareness of the threats of the youth and the coming to terms of their demands by the government and probably the genuine willing to listen to them and shun all that they (government and politicians and leaders) do that betray their trust. These stylistic devices present the youth as symbols of hope and agents of transformation. Proverbs embedded in the narrative not only critique the older generation's failures but also imply the possibility of regeneration if communal values are restored. The narrative's occasional shift in tone from satirical detachment to prophetic urgency reinforces the thematic message that societal renewal is inevitable if younger voices rise to leadership.

Literature as Social Discourse and Commentary

Taken together, these stylistic patterns show that *Our Children Are Coming* is not simply a story but a form of social discourse. As Fowler (1996) and Simpson (2004) remind us, literature often encodes ideology in its stylistic features, making form inseparable from content. In Ikeh's novel, the stylistic interplay of satire, imagery, rhetorical devices, and narrative voice both reflects and critiques Nigerian realities, turning the text into a medium of resistance and a call to collective action.

Discussion and Commentary

By undertaking the stylistic analysis of Chukwuemeka Ikeh's *Our Children Are Coming*, it is understandable to note how literary texts function as both aesthetic creations and instruments of social critique. This study, through the employment of stylistic analytical tools, has been able to demonstrate that Ikeh's novel employs style not merely for artistic effect but as a vehicle for interrogating Nigeria's

socio-political realities. The findings reveal broader implications for the study of Nigerian literature and its role in shaping national consciousness.

Literature as a Mirror and Critic of Society

A significant finding in this study is the fact that Ikeh's stylistic strategies as employed in this text, particularly satire, irony, and rhetorical questions provide deep social commentary on the themes of the text which are corruption, moral decay, and generational betrayal. This position makes the text very relevant to the African literature focus as it aligns with what Achebe (1975) says is the long standing tradition in African literature of employing fiction as a mirror of society. African literature, from right from early days when Chinua Achebe and Ngũgĩ wa Thiong'o, held sway, has consistently functioned as a "social conscience," using narrative artistry to critique leadership failures and articulate collective frustrations. *Our Children Are Coming* is an important example of this trajectory, but with an intensified focus on generational conflict and the promise of renewal through youth insistence and doggedness in enthroning the ideal society for their future.

CONCLUSION

This study has examined Chukwuemeka Ikeh's *Our Children Are Coming* through a stylistic perspectives, using analytical tools of stylistics: narrative technique, diction, imagery, and rhetorical devices to interrogate how this tools deployed by the author contribute to the novel's thematic concerns and social commentary. The analysis demonstrates that Ikeh's stylistic choices are not just for entertainment but has serves a critical function as vehicles for critiquing corruption, exposing generational conflict, and gesturing toward moral renewal. And by doing this, the novel transforms aesthetic form into a platform for social critique and civic engagement.

The findings project the importance of stylistics as a critical tool in literary analysis. Stylistics, unlike thematic or purely content-based studies, allows scholars to uncover the linguistic and rhetorical mechanisms through which meaning and ideology are constructed. In this novel, stylistic analysis has proven how the text encodes resistance to corrupt leadership while simultaneously empowering and encouraging the youth as symbols of hope and renewal.

The study, furthermore highlights the enduring role of African literature, like other literature globally, as a medium of social discourse and a catalyst for national reflection. In addressing issues that remain central to African and Nigeria's political and cultural landscape, as the themes in this text, the author contributes to an ongoing dialogue about the future of the African nations. The research thus underscores the importance of literature not only as an artistic endeavor, but also as a critical force for shaping consciousness and inspiring transformation.

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